

Project Planning

Tip 1: Contact the Research Data Management (RDM) Team Early

Develop a
Preliminary
Management
Strategy

Estimate Cost
of Data Storage
and Archiving

Assess Project
for Unique
Infrastructure
Needs

Tip 2: Consider a Data Management Plan

What is a DMP?

What: A DMP is a living document that includes information about data collection, processing, analysis, archiving, publishing, and reuse. Essentially, it is a road map that describes how your project will handle data throughout the research cycle. It can also detail the rights and responsibilities of project members and can address any ethical or legal considerations.

Why: DMPs help researchers stay organized and provide record of goals, plans, and responsibilities. Having this knowledge in one document helps prevent data loss and the improper use of data. It also facilitates data reuse and minimizes the risk of conflict between stakeholders.

How: DMPs be challenging to write, but the univie RDM team is here for you!

What to Include in a DMP

1. How will you store data during your project? Opt for automated back-up and storage options whenever possible.
2. Decide how you will document your data, what file formats you will use long-term.
3. Indicate what licenses you will assign to your outputs, like data, software, and hardware.
4. Consider long-term preservation. what repositories and archives would be a good home per for your data, software, hardware, and publications.
5. Indicate who is responsible for ensuring the DMP is followed. Duties can be divided.

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.